

Clicks to Campaigns: The Social Media Exposures on College Students' Political Engagement

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Abstract

The rise of social media has significantly altered how information is shared and consumed, leading to questions about its impact on various aspects of life, particularly in relation to political engagement. Social media has emerged as a powerful tool in modern society, shaping opinions, spreading information, influencing behaviors, and driving discussions on critical issues, including political awareness and active civic engagement worldwide. This investigation seeks to elucidate the connection between social media exposure and political engagement, while evaluating its significance in modern society. The study comprised 300 participants, including first to fourth-year students. This study employs a quantitative approach and adopts a descriptive-correlational design. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test indicated a deviation from normal distribution in the data. Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) showed a moderate positive correlation between social media use and political participation among the 300 participants ($r = 0.472$, $p < 0.001$). Students reported high social media use ($M = 3.46$, $SD = 0.53$), but relatively low political engagement ($M = 2.51$, $SD = 0.724$). Linear regression analysis confirmed social media use as a significant predictor of political participation ($B = 0.724$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting a positive relationship. This indicates that higher social media use may be associated with greater political involvement, despite the overall low level of engagement.

Keywords: *social media exposure, political engagement, correlation.*

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Introduction

Social media has now assumed a central position in politics and plays a huge role. The use of the internet by the public, especially in political campaigns and causes. This research investigates the impact of social media exposure on the political engagement of learners in higher education. College students are often considered a pivotal demographic in shaping the future of democratic engagement. This study aims to elucidate the role of digital platforms as catalysts for political awareness, discourse, and action by analyzing the relationship between offline political participation and online content consumption.

Lorenz-Spreen et al. (2023) stated that a prominent and contested subject currently is the causal connection between the worldwide utilization of digital media and the erosion of democratic principles. Moreover, Jones-Jang (2021) observed that, despite the increasing body of research on fake news and disinformation, there is a notable lack of empirical studies addressing the social and political consequences of exposure to inaccurate information.

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Furthermore, the digital era has significantly altered individuals' perceptions of the world. It is fundamental to comprehend the impact of social media accessibility on Filipino adolescents' understanding of national issues and their political engagement (Ibardelozza et al., 2022). Young individuals have historically played a significant role in Philippine politics; however, Generation Z predominantly utilizes social media for activism, online discourse, and initiating political movements (Velasco et al., 2024).

Social media has emerged as a vital tool for fostering political engagement among students. Sites such as Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook displays students with political content and allow them to post, comment, and share it, involving themselves in politics. Through social media, its understanding has been highly boosted among political matters, political personalities, and political positions, in the process demonstrating its function as an effective tool for increasing awareness and participation involving the scholarly population.

Prior research, on the other hand, has focused on the various factors controlling political participation, particularly among newly established or seasoned voters, and the lack of more concentrated college attention in Mindanao, the present region of the Philippines. This research aims at assessing the effect of social media coverage on the political activity of college students in this area. The findings will give enough information to enable the student to participate in politics in an informed and constructive manner.

Objectives

This research intends to investigate the correlation between social media exposure and political engagement among college students at the University of Mindanao Digos College. To attain this purpose, the study addressed the following specific inquiries:

1. To assess the level of social media exposure.
2. To determine the level of political engagement.
3. To determine the relationship between social media exposure and college students' political engagement.
4. To determine if social media exposure predicts political engagement.

Materials and Methods

Research Participants

The data shown in Table 1 exclusively encompassed students from all departments and year levels at the University of Mindanao Digos College for the 2024–2025 academic year. The researchers employed a convenience sample method for their investigation. Convenience sampling, as articulated by Rahi (2017) and cited by Golzar et al. (2022), involves the collection of data from a research population that is readily available to the investigator. Furthermore, both quantitative and qualitative research commonly employs convenience sampling as a non-probability sampling strategy. The researchers employed convenience sampling by selecting readily accessible and pertinent students from the University of Mindanao Digos College for the study. This approach enabled the researchers to gather data effectively inside the immediate academic setting. Still, it has some built-in problems, such as being prone to systematic error and sampling biases, not being able to properly interpret the p-value, not being representative of the whole population, not taking variability into account, and producing results that can't be used outside of the sample.

The respondents consist of 300 college students who have the option to participate in or withdraw from the study. The participants will decide whether to discard or retain all data. The majority of participants are first-year students (n=197, 65.67%), followed by second-year students (n=56, 18.67%), third-year students (n=28, 9.33%), and fourth-year students (n=19, 6.33%), who represent the smallest group.

Ultimately, the participants with the highest number of respondents by sex are female participants (n=204, 68%), while male participants have the lowest number of respondents (n=96, 32%).

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents (n=300)

PROFILE	f	%
SEX		
Female	204	68
Male	96	32
YEAR LEVEL		
1 st	197	65.67
2 nd	56	18.67
3 rd	28	9.33
4 th	19	6.33
TOTAL	300	100.0

Research Instrument

Data was collected using two questionnaires adapted from previous research: the Use of Social Media and its Reflection on the Political Participation of Youth Questionnaire (Zaky and Mohamed Taha, 2022) and the Political Participation Scale (Gopal and Verma, 2017). The Use of Social Media questionnaire, consisting of 12 items evaluated on a 5-point Likert scale (1=never to 5=always), demonstrated reliability and validity, indicating consistent results following repeated administration. SPSS calculated the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, resulting in a value of 0.799, indicating a high and acceptable degree of internal consistency for the research aims. The Political Participation Scale, developed using a deductive scale technique based on established frameworks (Churchill, 1979; Benter & Bonnet, 1980; Anderson & Gerbing, 1982; Begozzi et al., 1991; Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994; Hinkin, 1995), initially comprised 32 items. The items were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale from "Always" to "Never." A panel of 10 academicians conducted an expert evaluation that validated the content, resulting in the elimination of six items due to redundancy, ambiguity, or possible misinterpretation. An expert evaluation and recommended modifications were implemented in a pilot research involving 50 participants. The findings indicated that Cronbach's alpha was 0.872, beyond the acceptable threshold of 0.7 established by Nunnally (1994), signifying adequate internal consistency. The revised scale underwent further analysis, and the final items were reassessed for internal consistency. SPSS calculated a Cronbach's alpha of .78, signifying a substantial level of internal consistency.

The researchers performed pilot testing to evaluate the validity and reliability of both questionnaires in the Philippine context, specifically at the University of Mindanao Digos College. The questionnaire on "Use of Social Media and its Reflection on the Political Participation of Youth" proved validity through the Pearson-r Correlation Coefficient and demonstrated nearly perfect reliability, indicated by a Cronbach's Alpha rating of 0.997. Gopal and Verma (2017) derived the Political Participation Scale, which consists of 18 items. Pilot testing indicated that all questions, with the exception of item 4, were valid according to the Pearson-r Correlation Coefficient. A Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.994 signifies nearly flawless dependability for the scale. The researchers used a Likert scale to evaluate the relevant interpretations.

Table 2. Social Media Exposure Mean Interpretation

Mean Interval	Descriptive Rating	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Always	The social media exposure is always observed by the college students.
3.40-4.19	Often	The social media exposure is often observed by the college students.

2.60-3.39	Sometimes	The social media exposure is sometimes observed by the college students.
1.80-2.59	Seldom	The social media exposure is seldom observed by the college students.
1.00-1.79	Never	The social media exposure is never observed by the college students.

Table 3. Political Engagement Mean Interpretation

Mean Interval	Descriptive Rating	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Always	The political engagement is always observed by the college students.
3.40-4.19	Often	The political engagement is often observed by the college students.
2.60-3.39	Sometimes	The political engagement is sometimes observed by the college students.
1.80-2.59	Seldom	The political engagement is seldom observed by the college students.
1.00-1.79	Never	The political engagement is never observed by the college students.

Design and Procedure

This research is quantitative and utilizes a descriptive-correlational design. Initially, the researchers gathered pertinent literature for this investigation. The premise that social media significantly influences political engagement constituted the basis for the research. Users encounter political information via social media platforms, which facilitate civic engagement, awareness, and discourse. This notion aligns with theories suggesting that digital tools, especially for youth, act as catalysts for political mobilization. The research, centered on the student population of the University of Mindanao Digos College, was conducted within this framework. Given their regular usage of social media, we selected this cohort as a relevant demographic to examine how political content on digital platforms impacts their political engagement. This approach enabled the researchers to analyze specific behaviors inside a local academic environment. The researchers employed validated questionnaires from Zaky and Mohamed Taha (2022) and Gopal and Verma (2017), addressing the Use of Social Media and its Impact on Youth Political Participation and the Political Participation Scale, respectively, with minor adjustments and revisions. The researchers administered printed surveys to the potential respondents through conventional distribution methods. Before distributing the surveys, the researcher dispatched letters of authorization to conduct the study, which were endorsed by the advisor and positively supported by the Dean of the University. They also supplied letters to participants to uphold the ethical standards of the research. Finally, the researchers organized and analyzed the gathered data employing appropriate statistical methods, specifically utilizing IBM Statistical Package version 25 for the Social Sciences (IBM SPSS 25). The analysis and interpretation were conducted in accordance with the primary research objective.

Statistical Treatment

This study employed non-parametric statistical approaches according to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test ($D= 0.073, p < .001$) revealing a non-normal data distribution. Means and standard deviations, descriptive statistics appropriate for interval or ratio data (Crossman, 2019), delineated social media exposure and political activity. The mean represented the average levels, and the standard deviation (Hargrave, 2024) indicated variability. Spearman's rho, a non-parametric correlation coefficient suitable for non-normally distributed data at ordinal, interval, or ratio levels (Glen, 2021), examined the association between these variables. This facilitated proper analysis, augmenting reliability and validity. Non-parametric tests are essential when normalcy assumptions are breached, a frequent occurrence in social science (Crossman, 2019). Linear regression analysis examined the impact of differences in one variable on another

(Mahbobi, 2015). These methodologies, in conjunction with the normalcy test, facilitated comprehensive data analysis and significant results.

Ethical Consideration

Researchers prioritize ethical research techniques. Prior to consenting to participate, individuals are thoroughly apprised of the study's objectives, potential hazards, and methodologies. Participants are assured they may exit from the study at any moment without consequences. All collected data is kept completely secret, guaranteeing that participant names are not linked to any particular response. Although participants are not directly compensated, the study aims to increase knowledge of how social media affects young adults' political participation. Future research and initiatives aimed at encouraging informed civic engagement may benefit from this understanding. By citing all the sources required and ensuring the genuine collection and analysis of information, the study remains academic integrity. Potential conflicts of interest are, as a result, aired. Furthermore, before the data that the author collected for this work, the appropriate permits were also received from the respective institutional authorities.

Results

The Level of Social Media Exposures and Political Engagement of College Students

Table 4. The Level of Social Media Exposures and Political Engagement of College Students

Indicator	X	SD
Social Media Exposures	3.46	0.53
Political Engagement	2.51	0.724

The mean social media exposure score of 3.46 suggests a relatively high level of social media use among the college students in the study. The description of the results as "often" further supports this conclusion.

The mean score of political engagement is 2.51 suggests a relatively low level of political engagement among the college students in this study. The qualitative description of the engagement as "seldom" reinforces this interpretation.

Relationship between Social Media Exposures and Political Engagement

Table 5. Summary of Spearman Rho Correlation between Social Media Exposures and Political Engagement Among Participants

	Political Engagement
Social Media Exposure	0.472 0.001

There is a statistically significant and moderately strong positive correlation ($r = 0.472$, $p < 0.001$) between social media exposure and political engagement among the 300 participants. This suggests that increased social media exposure is associated with increased political engagement.

Social Media Exposure predicts Political Engagement

Table 6. Summarizes the Social Media Exposures on the Political Engagement

Predictor Variable	B	SE (B)	β	P-value
Social Media Exposure	0.724	0.067	0.530	0.000
R²		0.281		
F		116.317		

The linear regression analysis reveals a strong positive and statistically significant relationship ($B = 0.724$, $p < 0.001$) between social media exposure and political engagement. Social media exposure accounts for approximately 28.1% of the variance in political engagement. This suggests that increased social media use is associated with increased political engagement.

Discussion

The findings reveal that participants spend much time on social media ($X = 3.46$, $SD = 0.53$), with the results grouped as 'often'. This means the company is active on social media and will engage regularly among college students of the University of Mindanao Digos College. This study corroborates the Vaccari & Valeriana (2021) study and points to a significant role of social media in encouraging political participation and enhancing awareness of divergent political views, as well as in spreading political news, arguing political issues, and encouraging the public to engage in politics. Boulianne and Theocharis (2020) acknowledge the side effects of using social media among youths while at the same time stressing its positive potential for increasing cognitive and civil-political engagement. Such observation that college students patronize social media further validates its useful effect, suggesting that use of such terms may increase their interest in politics.

The mean score of political engagement of the participants was 2.51 ($SD = 0.724$), embodying a symbolic image of political engagement described as 'seldom' among college students at the study. This discovery is in tune with the findings of other researchers. As Ibardeola et al. (2022) have stressed, young people hardly get political. In its turn, the research also focuses on the shifts that are activated by the existence of a digital age in people's perceptions emphasizing that one needs to understand how the great connectivity and openness of social media influence the perceptions that Filipino adolescents have on national affairs and political involvement. Grasso & Giugni (2022) stressed that youngsters are likely to participate in activities that are not usually associated with political processes; this is due to the use of protest movements. This means that the rare engagement may not be a signal of passive political earnestness but an admiration of change in the sad prospect of how young people engage in politics. Despite the fact that public relations research remains a comparatively young academic discipline, it often predicts its engagement but, in fact, is hardly ever seen, as noted by Canel et al. (2022).

It indicates that there is a moderate positive correlation between social media exposure and political engagement (r value = 0.472, $p < 0.001$, $N = 300$). As social media exposure increases, political engagement tends to increase as well. Ida et al.'s (2020) research in Indonesia and Pakistan supports the positive relationship, demonstrating how social media facilitates youth political participation, enhances knowledge, and builds political efficacy. Similarly, Kim and Ellison (2022) highlight social media's role in facilitating offline political engagement through increased visibility and social learning. However, our findings present a more nuanced picture than some previous research. Although Ida et al. (2020) and Kim et al. (2022) point to generally positive effects, the moderate correlation strength indicates social media's influence isn't universally strong. Oser and Boulianne (2020) raise concerns about potential increases in political participation inequality due to digital media, highlighting uneven distribution of benefits. Moreover, the limited theoretical understanding of the psychological processes involved (Knoll

et al., 2020) necessitates further research to fully explain the complex interplay between social media and political engagement.

In the Philippines, where youth political involvement is historically significant, the relationship between social media use and political engagement is particularly complex. Generation Z, highly digitally engaged, has largely shifted activism from offline to online spaces, using social media platforms to advocate for causes and participate in political discourse (Ching Velasco et al., 2024). This aligns with the understanding that social media improves access to political information and resources for Filipino youth (Bunquin, 2020). However, the abundance of online information, both accurate and inaccurate, creates a challenging environment requiring careful navigation of political discussions and verification of sources (Calosa et al., 2023).

Studies show a strong link between social media use and political participation. A linear regression analysis yielded a positive and statistically significant coefficient ($B = 0.724, p < 0.001$), indicating a direct relationship. This aligns with Ohme's (2021) suggestion that exposure to like-minded views online can increase political polarization, potentially strengthening pre-existing beliefs rather than encouraging diverse viewpoints. Research by Alodat et al. (2023) supports this, demonstrating a positive correlation between social media and political engagement among young Jordanians. While social media can boost political involvement, it's also associated with increased division, particularly within specific demographics like the Jordanian youth population.

Conclusion

This research examined the connection between social media use and political participation among University of Mindanao Digos College students. Students reported frequent social media use ($M = 3.46, SD = 0.53$), but less frequent political engagement ($M = 2.51, SD = 0.724$). A moderate, positive correlation ($r = 0.472, p < 0.001$) emerged, suggesting a link between increased social media exposure and greater political involvement.

These findings support previous research highlighting social media's complex influence on young people's political behavior. Further research should explore factors like preferred platforms, content types, and peer influence to gain a deeper understanding of this relationship. Employing more sophisticated sampling methods, such as stratified random sampling based on academic year or political leaning, would improve the representativeness of future studies. Colleges could use these results to develop programs promoting critical media literacy and responsible online political participation.

Limitations include the study's focus on a single institution, potentially limiting generalizability. Reliance on self-reported data introduces potential bias, including social desirability effects and recall issues. Longitudinal studies across diverse academic settings would provide a richer understanding of the evolving relationship between social media exposure and political engagement.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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